

ISic1126

I.Sicily inscription 1126

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Sicily

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140611

1. [Διό]γενε [ς —] ΛΙ [—]
2. [χρησ]τὲ καὶ ᾠ-
3. [μεμ]πτε χαῖ [ρ] ε ,
4. [— —] ἔζησ [ε] ἔτ η [—]
5. [— —] ΑΚΓΑΜΠC [— —]
6. [— —] ΛΙΝ μήτηρ [— —]
7. [— —] ἐποί[η]σε [— —]
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492739

EDCS 39102283

PHI 140611

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

At 14.0307 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5575

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